

The Salary and Benefits of Catechists of St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariate, Archdiocese of Nueva Segovia, Philippines and Their Teaching Performance

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Abstract: This study aimed to determine the correlation between the salary and other benefits of the St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariate Catechists and their teaching performance during the school year 2019- 2020. To carry out the study, theories on motivation, the role of money as a source of motivation, the role of salaries and benefits for the employees were discussed and these theories were supported by the reviews of related literature and studies. To gather the data, the validated questionnaires were used. The data were analyzed using statistical tools such as the weighted mean and the Pearson r. Weighted mean was used to determine the adequateness of salaries and benefits and Pearson Product Moment Coefficient was used to determine the relationship between the salary and other benefits and the teaching performance of the respondents. The findings of the study are the following:

1. The computed mean,(2.14)shows that as a whole, the salary and other benefits were “Inadequate”.
2. As indicated by the computed mean, (4.24) as a whole the catechists were “Very Competent”
3. On the relationship between Salary-Benefits and Teaching Performance of Catechists St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariate, Archdiocese of Nueva Segovia Catechist is found to be significantly correlated. There is a significant correlation between the Salary-Benefits of the Catechists of St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariate and their Teaching Performance. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted.

Keywords: *Salary, benefits, Catechists, Vicariate, teaching performance*

I. Introduction/ Rationale

Teaching religion is the main duty and responsibility of Catechists assigned in the parishes. Their work is not different from other teachers working in other schools. What makes them different is that they are teaching Catechism only which is under the guidance of the parish priest and are paid by the parish. Just like any teacher who is working in other schools or those who are not called catechists, they are given salary as remuneration of their teaching job. Salary has become a basic requirement to accept the job or not because it is still considered as the main motivator for someone to exert effort on a certain job. In line with this thought, is the idea that workers are motivated mainly by pay, that workers will have the initiative to do work if they are paid (Taylor, 1956) (cited from the work of Teebom, 2018). Motivated employees help the organization to survive (Zafar et al., 2014). In addition to this, no other motivational technique can be closer to money and its instrumental value (Locke, Feren, McCaleb, Shaw, and Denny (1980) (cited from the work of Judge et al, 2010). For some, money is the only instrument to fulfil basic needs or to sustain everyday life. That is why money has become the main motivation when someone is applying for a job, particularly for poor people. People are usually happy to perform a job when they are paid well but they are not performing well when they are not paid well to meet their basic needs. In some certain context money is one of the sources of motivation and an essential factor in the success of every work. It cannot be denied that money serves as motivation for employees, and it is necessary to put in mind that employees are the building blocks of an organization. Motivated employees result in a progressive organization, therefore the success of an organization depends on conjoint efforts of the employees. According to Locke

and Latham (1984), money is important to goal setting because with such incentive, results in a person's being more committed to exert effort to attain a goal level than not offering the incentive (cited from the work of Cynthia lee, 1988)

It is a fact that in our context (poor countries) people are working for their daily needs and to satisfy their physical needs. Maslow (1943) has discussed this point that the most basic needs of human are physiological needs (cited from the work of McLeod, 2018). Physiological needs are existential needs because, without them, human beings cannot survive. The physiological needs refer to food, water, clothing and other biological needs. These are the basic needs that are needed to sustain daily life to survive. To provide these basic needs, one needs money. As Maslow (1943) regarded, that money is most strongly related to well-being when it is used to help satisfy basic needs (cited from the work of Howell et al, 2013). Indeed, past work showed that money is associated with well-being in poor communities (Biswas-Diener & Diener, 2001; Diener & Lucas, 2000; Howell, Howell, & Schwabe, 2006) (cited from the work of Howell et al, 2013)

Since money is used to motivate an employee not just to work well but to show his commitment to his work; thus, Locke (1976) argues that money as compensation can be adequate if it at least satisfies "economic, psychological, growth and motivational needs of workers" for them to stay in the job and be motivated (cited from the work of Sule, 2015). It cannot be denied that good performance comes from a good salary. Thus, Murakami (n.d) argues that employees seek some kind of compensation from what they put up in the job. For poor employees, money is a primary motivating factor to continuously push themselves to strive for greater heights.

It is along with those concepts, the current researchers would like to investigate the salary of catechists in St. Paul Vicariate and St. Mark Vicariate of Nueva Segovia Archdiocese and to find out their teaching performance. It is a common knowledge that Catechists' salaries have been neglected and such situation deserves investigation to have an idea whether the salary is still the main motivating factor for the catechists or not.

The objective of the Study

The purpose of the study is to provide information for school for the school to discuss with the bishop and parish priest about the policies on hiring the catechists and how the catechists are treated. Further, the output of the study will provide ideas for the parish priest in St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariates to establish a common policy on the salary of the catechists working in their vicariate.

Theoretical Framework

The following discussion presents different theories and concepts regarding salary and benefits and how they affect the performance of every employee- catechist.

Understanding Motivation

In discussing motivation, it is good to put in mind and have a clear idea of what motivation is. According to Rutherford (1990), motivation is the driving force to work effectively in an organization because according to him a motivated person can be creative (cited from the work of Manzoor, 1905). It is something that moves the person to action and continues him in the course of action already initiated (Dubin, 1958) (cited from the work of James, 2008). It is believed that one of the most important factors that affect human behaviour is motivation, thus results in different levels of performance. That is why, a motivated individual is impelled to do something, (Ryan and Deci, 2000).

A person may opt to do a thing to a certain extent pending on motivated behaviour. Since motivation is a very important factor to move an individual to achieve his goal, it is also important to know that motivation is the guiding principle that enables a person to stay focused on the path of success no matter what challenges come. Robin & Judge (2008) posited that motivation is the process that accounts for an individual's intensity, direction and perseverance of effort toward attaining the goal (cited from the work of Afful-Broni, 2012). This means that motivation determines how much efforts a person puts in his work. Wesson et. al., (2010) posited that motivation originates within and outside the person which initiates an effort related to work (cited from the work of Wanjihia, 2016).

In the self -determination theory, motivation can be distinguished in two types, the extrinsic, which refer to certain ways that comes from external sources and results in external reward, and intrinsic, which refer to doing something because it is enjoyable and interesting, (Deci & Ryan, 1985) (cited from the work of Ackerman, 2018). External

motivation keeps a person on the job because of external rewards and puts more time to a given task, (Klein, Goodhue, & Davis, 1997) (cited from the work of Danish et. al, 2015)

Motivation, therefore, may answer the question of why the workers do what they do. In line with such argument, Baron (1983) views motivation as a set or consequence of actions involved in the push and pulls forces that reinforce the task of the employee towards the attainment of definite achievement (cited from the work of Mensah & Tawiah, 2015). It is a process in which people are encouraged to move ahead for performing something extraordinary to accomplish their basic needs and get fully satisfied (Butkus & Green, 1999) (cited from the work of Tawiah, 2015). It inspires a person to move and do work to attain and meet the needs of the body. Thus, Vroom (1964) "argued that motivation is a process to govern individual choices among different choices and different forms of voluntary activities" (cited from the work of Shkuro, 2011).

Money as the source of Motivation

Every individual has their sources of motivation to perform their responsibilities. Some may be motivated by other things such as self-fulfilment, self-satisfaction, self-esteem and belongingness but not few people are motivated by money particularly with those who are still struggling with their basic needs. For them, money is still an important factor and remains the main reason why they work. In this case, money is very important for an employee to be motivated in the workplace (Taylor, 1911)(cited from the work of Franklin, n.d). Money helps to meet the physiological needs of the individual (Howell, et al, 2012). Workers entered into an organization to work, and in exchange, a reward or pay for their labour (Muo, 2007) (cited from the work of Sule et al, 2015). Thus, for worker's money is very important to support their daily needs. This is the case of poor countries like the Philippines, money matters the most. Many people are struggling to meet their daily needs and thus continue to live in poverty. Though some are employed they are employed in a "poor-quality job" that pays less than of the work they do (Galang, 2018). Within this environment, money becomes the main reason why people are looking for jobs. This is confirmed by studies. According to the study of Kulchamanov and Kaliannan (2014), money is still the strongest and compulsory factor for employees which can only satisfy basic needs. When money is used to attain their basic needs there is a possibility that money has a big impact on the life of employees. It serves as their guiding principle to make their job successful. Money is a real motivator for an employee.

The above arguments reveal that money influences maintain and motivate individuals to do a higher level of performance (Stanley, 2012) (cited from the work of Waiyaki, 2017). This is also supported by the argument of Taylor (1911) that money is a great motivator for industrial workers for higher productivity (cited from the work of Ghazanfar et al, 2011). Therefore, the pay is one of the means to fulfil the physical needs and by meeting the physical needs, people are influenced, and motivated and consequently it will affect the employee's performance. Thus money is so important for people who are raising a family. Some people are considered as the "breadwinner", in which other people in the family depend on them to meet their daily needs and usually, these are poor people. One of the things an employee is looking at when applying for the job is, how much the salary will be for the job they will do because they are trying to figure out such salary can meet their budget and for them to plan for their lives.

Monetary incentive is highly regarded as a sufficient means to motivate an employee and do a good performance (Smith and Hitt, 2005) (cited from Waiyaki, 2017). Also, Lawler (1971, 1981) argued that "compensation is a major policy lever that organization use to motivate employee attraction, performance, and retention, (cited from the work of Gerhart & Fang, 2015). Barber (2010) also explained that employees are not motivated to work when they are not being paid enough because it is against the reason why they are looking for jobs which are money. That is why according to Arnulf (2014) money is the most powerful motivator. He believes that money pushes a worker to give his very best when he is paid accordingly. Daniel Kahneman (2000) who received the Nobel Prize said: "the brain can be influenced by money" (Arnulf, 2014). In this way, when an individual does work, he keeps in his mind that at the end of his work he receives money. Pay may increase the performance of an employee, and the more they are paid well, the more they perform because what they are looking for is achieved (Gardner et al, 2004) (cited from team bay). Money talks and it talks loudly and clearly (Furnham, n.d). This means that the value of money is important to every person. In short, in performing job money is important. It serves as the main motivation for certain people. Therefore, Furnham (2012) added that extra money motivates people to render extra work.

The role of Salary and benefits to the life of employees

Salary is the most powerful means to motivate people (Bartleby research, 2013). Salary plays an important role in the lives of employees because through it people can meet their basic needs. It is the same with benefits because it helps employees to meet their basic needs. According to the studies of Seniwoliba, (2015) Salaries and benefits, equitable compensation and fair pay for their work are considered as the most prominent and important factor in job satisfaction. Donohoe, (2018) argues that compensation and benefits are the rewards they earn for the work they do. Salary is the payment given to an employee in return to his service to an organization, (McNamara, n.d). According to Merriam Webster's Dictionary, salary is given fixed compensation for the services. The amount of salary is important for employees because it motivates people to work. Employees are expecting a fair return to their exerted effort. As Obasan,(2012) pointed out that salary is to help employees become motivated, contributing to the productivity and growth of an organization (cited from the work of Sule, et. al, 2015). Employees are working because they have families to support and thus salary very significant to motivate them. Though not all people, not all countries are working only for money but countries that belong to low class, such as the Philippines, salary is very important because it serves its purpose, in other words, no work no pay, no pay no life. Life is dependent on money and money is dependent on the work that one has contributed to the company. Money serves as the biggest tool for man to live.

Benefits are cash or non - cash is given to the employees on the top of their basic salaries. Benefits can be classified as mandated and non-mandated or institutional benefits. Mandated benefits are benefits mandated by law such as SSS, Phil-health, Pag-Ibig, Sick-leave, vacation leave, etc. Institutional benefits are given by the institutions or the company beyond the mandated benefits such as 14th-month pay, transportation allowance, vacation allowance, etc. (Divine College of Vigan Manual, 2011). When the employees are assured of their benefits, they will not be worried about money.

Salaries and benefits are given to all who are working for a certain period, whatever the nature of the business. Catechists in the parish are also employees. They need to be compensated fairly according to the law. In this case, salaries and benefits must also be given to the Catechist because they are humans with the same needs as others. They need to be secured too in terms of salaries and benefits and also in terms of security of tenure. Even though service to God and the people is the main reason of their employment but their services must be compensated "Remain in the same house, eating and drinking whatever they provide, for the labourer deserves to be paid. Do not move about from house to house" (Luke 10:7, NRSV Bible.) A labourer indeed needs something that will compensate for his exerted effort. Even the Bible says that a man who gives his strength in service must be paid accordingly. The Bible speaks that anyone who fulfil a duty or do a work id deserving to be paid. In the statement of Cardinal Vidal (1987) that catechists need salary because they cannot live without it. It is a manifestation that in every workplace whether religious or not, employees must be compensated. Catechists are striving well to spread the good news, exerting so much effort and time, it is very important that they are compensated well.

Being a catechist is an employee with pay because they must be treated as employees with salaries and benefits entitled to an employee. They have basic needs to meet and have also families to support. Though money is not the primary reason why one wants to be a catechist but service or mission but a labourer deserves to be paid. They are motivated if they are compensated well but they can leave their work if they are not paid fairly. It is also one of the reasons why they are joining the ministry.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

In conducting this study, the researchers were guided by the following model:

Figure 1: The framework reflects the relationship between the salary and other benefits of the catechists and their teaching performance.

Statement of the Problem:

This study determined the relationship between the salary and other benefits of the Catechists of St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariates and their teaching performance.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. Based on the catechists' perception, what is the level or degree of adequacy of their salaries and other benefits?
2. Based on the evaluation of the teachers, in the school where the catechists teach, what is the level or degree of their teaching competence?
3. Is there a significant relationship between their salary and other benefits and their level of teaching competence?

Assumptions of the study

The study is guided by the following assumptions:

1. The data-gathering instruments are valid and reliable.
2. The answers of the respondents are honest.
3. Teaching performance is measurable.
4. Salary is a source of motivation for employees.

Hypothesis

The study is guided by the hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between the salary and other benefits of the catechists and their teaching performance.

Scope and Delimitation

The study delimits itself to the determination of the perception of the Catechists as to the adequacy of their Salary and other Benefits and their possible correlation with their Teaching Performance.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This part presents the pieces of literature that discuss motivation and money, salaries and benefits to the employees and also studies conducted by other researchers related to the same topic and support the current study.

Review of Related Literature

Motivation is a great factor in the workplace. An employee that is not motivated may affect his/her performance. Therefore, the management must be able to sustain a certain level of motivation for the employees to perform to their job well. When the motivation is enough to sustain the level of satisfaction, the more dedicated and productive they are. Shahzadi, et. al, (2014), opines that "employees' motivation is very important for organizations as every concern requires physical, financial and human resources to accomplish the goals." This means that motivation is involved in the workplace. Motivation is necessary for a person to move. There can be a lot of factors that can motivate employees such as the good relationship with co-workers, with employers, and good working environment but most of all money is the most influential motivator in a workplace. Dobre, (2013) opines that the value of money is very important and thus the amount of salary and benefits are also important for employees' motivation to strive towards high performance and to satisfy their needs such as physiological needs. Even though there can be other different reasons why an individual wants to join a company but it cannot be denied that people are looking for better pay or better salary in the first place, that is why people will not do a job without pay, (Kokemuller, 2017). They are motivated when they pay and other aspects of the employees are meeting their expectation. Money is what they are expecting from the company as a result of their labour because it is a means to support their lives and their family. Money makes things possible such as housing, clothing, food and almost everything. That is why Woods (n.d) argued that "people are often

motivated by money", and it is a motivation to earn a living. In this generation, where all the commodities are getting higher at price, employees are seeking pay that will equitably reciprocate their work.

Motivation is needed by all people including the catechists and the priests. Catechists in the parish are considered employees. They play a very important role in spreading the good news in schools and even in Barangays, both as full time and volunteer. Both are exerting effort to attain the goal of the catechetical programs of the diocese and the parish and all of them are employees of the diocese. There is only one distinction between the two groups. According to Katolisismo (n.d), a School-Based Volunteer Catechists- are those who commit themselves doing catechesis in public school together with the full-time catechists but only for a limited time, while full-time catechists are those who devote their lives completely to the service and recognized as such. However, whether one is a full time or a volunteer, both perform the same responsibility of catechizing the people. Both are joining hand in hand in the catechetical program.

Catechists are also required fair salary as mandated by law with the work they do to support their daily lives and their families. This was emphasized by Cardinal Vidal (1987), that professional catechists cannot live without salary and volunteer catechists need allowances for their training, teaching materials and transportation." Rerum Novarum by Pope Leo (1891) pronounced that "if one man hires out to another his strength or his skill, he may do so to receive in return what is necessary for the satisfaction of his needs." This means that a man who is working in an organization has to be compensated because he exhausts all his talents and skills for the organization. Leonard (2019) posited that people are looking for something that will stabilize their finance. He also added that "Properly compensating employees shows you value them as workers and as human beings." People think that when they are given just and equitable compensation the value of their life is recognized. Employees deserve compensation that is enough to reciprocate their exerted effort. In this case, Leonard (2019) concluded that people are becoming happy when they are compensated well and strive to remain in an organization because he is secured financially. Often they are forced to live the organization to look for a greener pasture. Many of our catechists have families to sustain. Compensation of catechists is not merely enough to raise a family. As Swain (n.d) discusses, that employers who pay their employees the minimum wage they reduce productivity compared to employees receiving a high salary. Salary matters when it comes to the fulfilment of needs. Nordmeyer (n.d) also pointed out further that employees are looking for a job that will fairly compensate their work, supported by Arthur (2018) that money can buy something that can be a help or useful to employees. It cannot be denied that most of the catechists working in a parish are married and have children. To sustain their life, they must have another business. In addition to this. It is also recognized that catechists are fully motivated when their needs are satisfied. They feel more secure when all their needs are met. Catechists need to be regarded as employees who are motivated to work for a living.

Teaching competency

Teaching is the act, the practice or profession of a teacher this is according to the definition from Merriam Webster Dictionary (1828), moreover, it also defines the meaning of competence which is "the quality or state of having knowledge, judgment, skill, or strength." Putting the two words together, we can say that teaching competence is the act or practice or profession of a teacher having the quality or state of having knowledge, judgment, skill or strength. To become competent in teaching, one must be skilful enough in the many strategies and techniques on how to teach the students. In addition to this, being competent as well is to become life enduring, life sacrificing and life-giving. Life enduring in a sense that he can give his full strength in the teaching field as defined by Webster's dictionary. Life sacrificing in a way that he can commit himself to share his knowledge. Life-giving because he can give a just and fair judgment.

Being competent in the teaching field is always becoming an effective teacher, supported by Sali-ot, (2011), that "effective teachers are equipped with a repertoire of best teaching practices such as strategies, procedures, and approaches in presenting, implementing and assessing classroom instruction following the objective set." Truly, being competent in teaching is first to become equipped, equipped in a way that he is confident enough to face his students, and being confident meaning being prepared and being knowledgeable about the lesson he will be giving to his students. Franklin (n.d) says "by failing to prepare, you are preparing to fail." It is logical to say that and putting it into the context that if a teacher is prepared and knows his lesson well he is confident enough to face his students.

Zulueta, (2005) says that a competent teacher should fully understand the methods and principles of teachings as well as the proper skills to be used as techniques and strategies (cited from the work of Andoy, et al, n.d). In this way,

teachers who are competent enough must share true to life experiences, profound knowledge and ideas about the lesson.

To describe a teacher being competent is also to speak about his development. The department of education has proclaimed an order (35) on 2016 that talks about the development of teachers to become competent, it states that, "DepEd fully supports the continuing professional development of its teaching personnel based on the principle of lifelong learning and its commitment to the development of teacher's potential aimed towards their success in the profession." This means that to be a competent teacher is to develop more the profession. The development in the teaching profession may result into becoming creative and innovative in presenting his lessons because in the first place being a teacher is being a critical and creative thinker, (Sacdalan, et al, n.d). This also means that teachers must provoke critical thinking by posing situations that will lead the students to reflect on the importance of the lesson in their day to day life. Sacdalan, et al (n.d) again proves this, she opines that teachers are competent if they are "resourceful, being a good motivator, being flexible in all type of students and being responsible in all tasks."

Being competent in teaching is also about using the 21st-century instructional materials such as the usage of projector and laptop and other instructional materials, this is supported by Pelligrino (2011), he states that to be an operative teacher he must use different media in his lessons (cited from the work of Catolos & Catolos, 2017). In our generation, today students are linked with the so-called e generation, which means that everything around us today is electronic gadgets. Teachers must be updated with the instructional materials they are using in the classroom so that the teaching and learning process will still relevant.

Review of Related Studies

Human motivation is the main challenge of the management of whatever nature the business is. Many businesses have neglected human resources motivation as a critical success factor in running the organization. As cited from the study of Ojeleye (2017) on the treatment of human resources found that many organizations have not given full attention to the motivation of the human resource and thus he reiterated that in an organization, human resource is the greatest assets and therefore employees' motivation must be given the greatest preference (Ojeleye & Okoro, 2016). Considering human as the best asset in an organization, motivation cannot be taken for granted (Ojeleye, 2017). Employees' motivation is an extreme factor that will drive them to work and perform at their best and when they are motivated, they are becoming truer to their commitment and feel more satisfied in their job. The study of Nguyen, (2017) proves that "employee motivation at work is considered as an essential drive as it generates effort and action towards work-related activities, for example, employee's willingness to spend energy to achieve a common goal. The finding of studies also reiterated the above findings that the effectiveness and efficiency of employees are likely to be limited if they are not motivated, (Aktar et al., 2012) (cited from the work of Hanaysha & Majid, 2018). Money is the most basic motivator for the employees to remain in their jobs, as it is shown in the study of Umali et, al. (2013) (cited from the work of Tan et al, 2019). They have found the relationship between the incentive and motivation to the employees in the selected fast food chains in Lipa, Batangas. They found that incentives such as first, money, mandatory benefits like SSS/Phil Health, PAG-IBig, the 13th-month pay, etc. are helpful and can increase productivity in the workplace (Umali et al, 2013). They also added that with such incentives, it can build loyalty between the employer and the employee and job satisfaction. Such a study just confirmed that salary is very important to employees and it cannot be undermined. This is supported by Author (2019) money is a medium of exchange for goods and services and a means of payment for good services or used for the settlement of financial obligations. Obasan (2012) also concluded that compensation strategy is the most important strategy because it influences the productivity and growth of an organization. Cited from the work of Manchia (2013), Heneman (1992) Diener & Biswas-Diener (2002) and Kasser & Ahuvia (2002) pointed out further that monetary is a source of motivation which is not a new one. Uche (n.d) found in his study that fair wages are a source of motivation. The more adequate and fair the compensation is, the more productive an employee will be. Furnham, (1996); Luna & Tang (2004), Medina, Gallegos & Lara, (2008), contended that "Money-based rewards are considered to be the most powerful motivator." (cited from the work of Monteiro et al., 2015).

As pointed out by Khan et al, (2017) that reward in the form of financial returns motivate the employee and can build employment relationship and loyalty. According to Agwu, M. O. (2013) as he quoted from Khan et al. (2017) that giving rewards such as financial reward to good performance motivate employees to improve their service better and money is the primary motivator to attract employment and this finding is supported by the study Ajayi, (2019), that money and other financial rewards are found to be main tools for motivating employees (Gikuya, 2014). There have been little studies on the non-monetary forms of motivation as effective tools for motivation by the management of

organizations, (quoted from the work of Ajayi 2019). Emeya & Antiaobong (2016), Chiang & Birtch (2010) discovered that salary and other benefits are good factors to arouse the interest of the teachers to teach. As pointed out by Ajmal (2015) that extrinsic reward such as money and other benefits are counted as "compensated value" that pushes an employee to put an extra effort to his work and more committed and satisfied in the work. This is confirmed by Khalid & Aftab (2017), that money as an extrinsic reward that motivates employees to increase performance and continuous commitment. It is in an exchange of the contribution of an employee to an organization, (Malkovich & Newman, 2008) (cited from the work of Khalid & Aftab, (2017). This is also supported by the study of Jasmi, (2012), that extrinsic reward is considered to have a positive effect in the performance of an employee.

A motivated employee depends on the extrinsic reward he is receiving. An employee that is not paid with wages may not do his work properly because no something pushes him to work. It is confirmed by Riasat et al (2016), that there is a positive relationship between extrinsic rewards and employee's motivation and satisfaction. This is further explained by the study of Tahir et al., (2011) that "compensation is the cornerstone of effective talent management." Cantanzaro (2001) pointed out that compensation "has a profound effect" to employees (cited from the work of Ayza, 2018). Supported by O'Reilly et al., (as cited Sarwar & Aburge, 2013) that extrinsic rewards made an employee more dedicated compared to intrinsic reward (cited from the study of Amin, 2016). Waal & Jansen (2013) found out that "monetary bonuses could increase productivity and job performances" (cited from the study of Amin, 2016). The success of an organization depends on extrinsically motivated employees. Employees who are motivated because compensated well will put all his efforts and talents to his work. Moreover, he will become more creative and innovative in doing his work. He is more eager and willing to put all his best and ability to create a successful organization.

Teaching Competency

In the study conducted by Saccalan, (n.d), she discovered that a competent teacher must be knowledgeable, has the abilities and beliefs and able to bring it to his teaching situation. In thin case teacher who is competent must be holistic. Holistic in a sense that he carries in himself a role model to his students. In the study of Mulyasa (2007) cited from the study of Rahmatullah, (2016) that "the competence has a role to improve the teacher's performance, the teacher who has a good competence will produce the best performance, the teacher's competence is qualitative of teacher behaviour nature meaningful. This stressed that a competent teacher is an effective teacher. An effective teacher can affect students' lives. That is why in the study of Drexel (2003) he concluded that a competent teacher is always obedient in doing the procedures of assessing and identifying the learning results, experienced, have sufficient knowledge and behave to the progress, (cited from the work of Rahmatullah, (2016).

In the study of Hasegawa, (n.d) he concluded that effective teachers who are also labelled as competent teachers must use technology in delivering the lesson to catch the attention of the students. Nowadays students are more interested to listen in a class if teachers will use a laptop, projector and different technology because we are in a generation which the young called the "e-generation" where everyone is technology-oriented. He also discovered that relevant strategies in teaching the students will improve students learning. Cited from the study of Hasegawa (n.d), Osakwe (2009) concluded that "teaching skills was one of the significant correlating factors and predictors of effective classroom interaction." It is always a fact that to be effective in the classroom, teachers must use various and relevant strategies that will arouse the interest of the students.

In the study conducted by Lardizabal (2003), he found that a competent teacher tests his students as cited from the study of Catolos & Catolos (2017). This means that an effective teacher always provokes questions that will make the students think critically. In this sense, an effective teacher also posts a situation that will make the students reflect on. Another study cited from the research of Catolos & Catolos (2017), the study of Lapuz (2010) found that to be a competent teacher, one must know the content of his lesson and confidently know how to explain it in a way that the students will understand it. To be an effective teacher one must be self-assured and knowledgeable enough in presenting his lessons to his students. He must be ready and prepared in the lessons he is giving to his students.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design, procedures in conducting this study, research instrument, the locale of the study, population, data gathering procedure and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive correlational research design. According to Parahoo (1997: 142), descriptive research is "a plan that describes how, when and where data are to be collected and analyzed". Polit et al (2001: 167) also define research design as "the researcher's overall for answering the research question or testing the research hypothesis".

A Correlation Research Method is used by the researchers to determine and identify the relationship between two different variables. Through this study, the researchers knew how much variation caused by one variable concerning the variation caused by the other variable.

Population

The respondents of the study were the catechists and teachers who are teaching in the schools where the catechists taught, within the 8 parishes of St. Paul Vicariate and 3 parishes of St. Mark Vicariate. The teachers evaluated the teaching competence of the catechists. The catechists assessed the degree or level of adequacy of the salary and other benefits they were receiving. There were 60 teachers and 114 catechists, a total of 174 respondents

The locale of the Study

The study was conducted at the 8 parishes located at St. Paul Vicariate and 3 parishes located at St. Mark Vicariate, Archdiocese of Nueva Segovia.

Data Gathering Administration

The researchers obtained permission from Priests of the different parishes of St. Paul the Apostle Vicariate, Archdiocese of Nueva Segovia, to conduct the study and float questionnaires in their assigned parishes. The researchers also requested the Catechist Coordinator of different parishes for his/her help to convince his/her Co-catechist to answer the questionnaires honestly.

Data Gathering Instrument

To gather data, sets of researchers-made questionnaires were utilized but before it was used the questionnaires were validated by a panel of experts to determine their content.

Statistical Treatment of the Study

For the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered, the statistical tools were used:

1. Weighted mean and over-all mean were used to measure the perception of the salary and teaching performance of the respondent.

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

2. Pearson Product Moment Coefficient was used to determine the relationship between the salary and the teaching performance of the respondents.

$$r = \frac{n\sum xy - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n\sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n\sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

In interpreting the data on the perception of the salary and benefits, the following norm was used:

Statistical Norm	Descriptive Rating
4.21- 5.00	Very Adequate
3.41- 4.29	Adequate
2.61- 3.40	Somewhat Adequate
1.81- 2.60	Inadequate

1.00- 1.80	Very Inadequate
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In interpreting the level of the teaching performance of the catechist, the following descriptive norm was used:

Statistical Norm	Descriptive Rating
4.21- 5.00	Very competent
3.41- 4.29	Competent
2.61- 3.40	Somewhat competent
1.81- 2.60	Incompetent
1.00- 1.80	Very Incompetent

IV. Findings

The findings of the study is presented according to the arrangement of the statement of the problems. The study wanted to determine the correlation between salary and benefits of the Catechists of St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariate, Ach Diocese of Nueva Segovia, Ilocos Sur and their teaching performance. Problems were proposed and the following are the findings.

Problem 1. Based on the catechists' perception, what is the level or degree of adequacy of their salaries and other benefits?

Table 1. Salary and other benefits of the Catechists of St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariate, Arch Diocese of Nueva Segovia.

ITEMS	X	Descriptive Rating
1. Salary, compensation or remuneration can support family expenses.	1.93	Inadequate
2. The salary can buy basic needs such as food, shelter, clothes, etc.	2.01	Inadequate
3. Benefits availed: SSS, Phil Health, PAG-IBIG, 13 th -month pay, 14 th -month pay, sick leave, vacation leave, maternity leave, etc.	1.93	Inadequate
4. Chalk allowance, instructional materials allowance and uniform allowance.	1.74	Very Inadequate
5. Travel allowance, going to school or in barangay and barrios.	3.11	Somewhat Adequate
Average Weighted x	2.14	Inadequate

Legend:

- 4.21- 5.00 - *Very Adequate*
- 3.41- 4.29 - *Adequate*
- 2.61- 3.40 - *Somewhat Adequate*
- 1.81- 2.60 - *Inadequate*
- 1.00- 1.80 - *Very Inadequate*

Based on the computed mean presented on the table, it shows that as a whole, the salary, benefits, compensation, remuneration of Catechists are 2.14 or "Inadequate". Even when taking it singly, salary, compensation or

remuneration is inadequate (1.93), they are inadequate to provide the basic needs (2.01). Even the mandated benefits (1.93), and chalk allowance (1.74) are inadequate. However, travelling allowance is somewhat adequate (3.11).

Problem 2. Based on the evaluation of the teachers, in the school where the catechists teach, what is the level or degree of their teaching competence?

Table 2. Teaching Performance of the Catechist of St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariate, Arch Diocese of Nueva Segovia.

ITEMS	X	Descriptive Rating
1. The catechist is confident and knowledgeable about the lesson.	4.66	Very Competent
2. The catechist is creative and innovative in presenting the lesson that can easily be understood.	4.30	Very Competent
3. The catechist can share experiences, knowledge and ideas about the lesson.	4.42	Very Competent
4. The catechist uses varied instructional materials in his or her lesson.	4.12	Competent
5. The catechist uses a motivational technique such as using the laptop and projector, games and the like in teaching his or her lesson.	3.75	Competent
6. The catechist provokes critical thinking by posing situations that will lead the students to reflect on the importance of the lesson in their day to day life.	4.16	Competent
Average Weighted x	4.24	Very Competent

Legend:

- 4.21- 5.00 - *Very competent*
- 3.41- 4.29 - *Competent*
- 2.61- 3.40 - *Somewhat competent*
- 1.81- 2.60 - *Incompetent*
- 1.00- 1.80 - *Very Incompetent*

As indicated by the computed mean presented on the table, it reveals that as a whole the catechists are “Very Competent” or 4.24, in regards their confidence and knowledge about the lesson (4.66), creativity and innovation in lesson presentation which can easily be understood (4.30), and in terms of sharing their experiences, knowledge and ideas about the lesson (4.42). They are also competent in terms of using varied instructional materials in their lesson (4.12), using motivational techniques such as using the laptop and projector, games and the like in teaching his or her lesson (3.75), provoking critical thinking by posing situations that will lead the students to reflect on the importance of the lesson in their day to day life (4.16).

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the salary and benefits and their level of teaching competence?

Table 3. Significant Relationship between salary and teaching performance

Motivational Factors	Teaching Performance
Salary and Benefits	0.2661*

*Significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Based on the correlation coefficient computation, it is found that Salary and Benefits have a significant correlation at 0.05 level (2-tailed) between salary and benefits and the teaching performance of St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariate Catechists. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study that there is a correlation between Salary-Benefits and Teaching Performance is accepted.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, it was found that the Salary and other Benefits of St. Paul and St. Mark Vicariate, Archdiocese of Nueva Segovia Catechists were "Inadequate" with the average mean of 2.14. The Over-all level of the teaching performance of the respondents was "Very Competent" as revealed by its over-all mean of 4.24. Generally, the Salary and other benefits were found to be significantly related to the Teaching Performance of the respondents with r (0.2661*) which was set at 0.5 level of significance.

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